

Computed *F*-ratios were significant at 1% in each case. N, K, and P levels used contributed positively and significantly

to boro rice yield and were ranked first, second, and third, respectively, in importance.

Of the plant nutrients, N and P levels used contributed positively and significantly to aman yield. □

Azolla — a supplemental nitrogen source for flooded rice culture

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In an experiment to evaluate the relative advantage of using *Azolla pinnata* as a supplemental source of nitrogen in combination with fertilizer urea, azolla was added at 5, 10, and 15 t/ha to plots fertilized with urea (see table). The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications at Rajendranagar during 1979-80 kharif. A uniform basal dose of 26 kg P/ha and 30 kg K/ha was applied to all plots. The variety used was Tellahamsa. The nitrogen content of azolla on wet weight basis was 0.25%.

Differences in grain and straw yields were significant among treatments. The

Yield of rice as influenced by azolla and inorganic nitrogen fertilization. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India.

Treatment	Grain		Straw	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over yield in control	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over yield in control
100 kg N/ha	3.7	185	4.3	139
87.5 kg N + 5 t azolla/ha	3.6	177	4.1	128
62.5 kg N + 15 t azolla/ha	3.4	162	3.9	117
75 kg N/ha	3.0	131	3.4	89
37.5 kg N + 15 t azolla/ha	3.0	131	3.4	89
50 kg N/ha	2.8	115	3.2	78
25.0 kg N + 10 t azolla/ha	2.7	108	3.1	72
12.5 kg N + 5 t azolla/ha	2.2	69	2.9	61
25 kg N/ha	2.0	54	2.8	56
Control	1.3	—	1.8	—
C.D. at 5%	0.6	—	0.4	—

highest grain yield — 3.7 t/ha — was obtained with 100 kg N/ha supplied through urea. It was significantly higher than that of the other treatments but on par with those obtained with 87.5 kg N + 15 t azolla/ha and 62.5 kg N/ha + 15 t azolla/ha. Similarly the grain yield with 37.5

kg N + 15 t azolla/ha was equal to that with 75 kg N/ha applied through urea. Differences among the other treatments were nonsignificant. In general the grain and straw yields were low because of late planting. □

Azolla as a substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in rice

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A study to assess the potential value of azolla as a substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in rice in sandy soils was made during 1981 kharif in Kerala.

Fourteen treatment groups in a randomized block design with 3 replications included azolla incorporation at 10 t/ha, azolla inoculation at 1 t/ha, a combination of incorporation and inoculation, and a combination of azolla inoculation and nitrogen fertilizer at 30 kg/ha, applied at basal, active tillering, and panicle initiation stages.

Grain yield (2.9 t/ha) and straw yield (3.0 t/ha) were greatest with basal incorporation of azolla combined with dual culturing and in situ incorporation at active tillering stage and 30 kg N/ha applied at panicle initiation. Several other treatments, including a treatment that

Grain and straw yield with azolla incorporation, Kerala, India, 1981.

Treatment ^a			Yield (t/ha)	
Basal	Active tillering	Panicle initiation	Grain	Straw
FN	FN	FN	2.2	2.6
AI	FN	FN	2.6	2.9
FN	AI	FN	2.8	2.9
FN	FN	AI	2.4	2.8
FN+DC	Aii	FN	2.7	2.8
FN+DC	FN	Aii	2.4	2.8
FN+DC	—	FN	2.5	3.0
FN+DC	FN	—	2.3	3.0
FN+DC	—	—	2.4	3.0
AI+DC	FN	—	2.7	3.1
AI+DC	—	FN	2.6	2.9
AI+DC	—	—	2.6	2.8
AI+DC	Aii	FN	2.9	3.0
AI+DC	FN	Aii	2.7	3.1
CD (0.05)			0.38	N.S.

^aFN = 30 kg N/ha, AI = azolla incorporation (10 t/ha), Aii = azolla in situ incorporation (dual culture), DC = dual culture (inoculation @1 t/ha).

received no N fertilizer, had similar yields. The treatment that received 90 kg N/ha in 3 equal splits recorded the lowest grain yield (2.2 t/ha) (see table).

Treatment results indicate azolla is an efficient substitute for N fertilizer in sandy soil where there is likely to be vertical and lateral leaching. This may be because azolla releases N slowly and steadily, thereby limiting N losses. □

Effect of phosphorus fertilizer placement on root and shoot growth of wetland rice

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A pot experiment was conducted to determine the effect of phosphorus (P) placement on root and shoot growth of wetland rice. P was applied to varieties IR42 and MR7 at 0 (surface application), 5, 10, and 15 cm soil depth in 6 replications. Pots were 35 cm in diameter and 45 cm deep. Ten kilograms of clay loam (pH 5.8, organic carbon 1.05%, 0.15% total N, 4 ppm available P, 0.26 meq exchangeable K/100 g, and 17.4 meq CEC/100 g) were added to each pot. Soil was puddled

and 22 kg P/ha (triple superphosphate) was applied at 4 depths. Urea (200 kg N/ha) and muriate of potash (25 kg K/ha) were broadcast. Remaining N was top-dressed at panicle initiation. Three replications were harvested at panicle initiation to record root and shoot dry weight and N, P, and K uptake. Grain yield was recorded for the remaining three replications.

Root and shoot dry weight and grain yield significantly increased for both varieties at 5-cm placement depth. Placing P at 10 and 15 cm decreased dry weights and grain yield (see table).

The linear relationship of root dry weight and dry yield had a highly significant correlation coefficient of 0.980 for both IR42 and MR7, indicating that placing P at the proper root zone enhanced root growth and increased grain yield. N, P, and K uptake was greater at 0 and 5 cm placement depths than at 10 and 15 cm, indicating that nutrients are utilized most effectively by plant roots when P is placed in their immediate vicinity (see figure). □

Effect of P placement depths on root and shoot dry weight at panicle initiation and yield of wetland rice, Sabah, East Malaysia.

Placement depth (cm)	IR42			MR7		
	Root dry wt (g/pot)	Shoot dry wt (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)	Root dry wt (g/pot)	Shoot dry wt (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)
0	3.7 b	22.85 b	155.6 b	3.6 b	27.41 b	154.5 b
5	4.3 a	25.77 a	165.8 a	4.4 a	30.32 a	166.0 a
10	3.5 b	21.30 c	153.1 c	3.5 b	24.3 c	152.8 c
15	3.2 bc	20.70 c	150.2 d	3.1 bc	24.10 c	150.8 d

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 0.05 level.

Changes in nutrient uptake by wetland rice at different depths of phosphorus placement at panicle initiation, Sabah, East Malaysia.

Response of prerelease rice cultures to nitrogen in light-textured soil

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A field trial during 1980 kharif (wet season) studied the response to nitrogen levels of four prerelease rices (Table 1) on a red sandy loam with low organic matter and phosphorus, moderate potash, and pH of 6.1. IR20 was the check variety. The treatments were replicated four times in a split-plot design with variety on the main plots and nitrogen levels on the subplots. A basal application of 22 kg P and 42 kg K per hectare was given. Nitrogen was applied 50% at transplanting, 25% at 25 days after transplanting (DT), and 25% at 45 DT.

IET2490 and IET2730 responded significantly up to 120 kg N/ha; KMP39 response leveled off beyond 80 kg N/ha (Table 2). All cultures except Mandya Vani were superior to IR20. □

Table 1. Characteristics of rices tested in Mandya, India.

Culture	Cross	Duration (days)	1,000-grain wt (g)
Mandya Vani	IR8/CR1014	128	17
IR20	IR262/TKM6	131	19
KMP39	Jaya/W1263	140	20
IET2730	IR8/Annapurna	141	32
IET2490	IR8/NP130	143	30

Table 2. Response of prerelease rice cultures to nitrogen in Mandya, India.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	Mandya Vani	IET2490	ET2730	KMP39	IR20
0	2.4	3.0	3.0	3.2	2.4
40	3.2	4.1	4.0	3.9	3.7
80	3.7	4.8	4.8	4.2	4.1
120	3.8	5.2	5.1	4.4	4.5
160	3.6	4.8	5.0	4.5	4.6
CD (0.05)	Varieties: 0.36		Nitrogen: 0.33		Interaction: NS
Cv (%)	11				

Methods of zinc application to rice on sodic soil

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Zinc (Zn) deficiency is a widespread nutritional disorder of rice, particularly in sodic soils under reclamation. A field experiment to correct the problem was carried out on Ghabdan loam soil (salic Natraqualf) in Sangrur district of Punjab.